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Citing soil and agricultural research data – Publication, DOI provision, citation and versioning of data published via the BonaRes Repository

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Title Citing soil and agricultural research data

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Abstract The rights of authors to their data and thus their right to be mentioned by name when data is reused are valuable assets and are therefore stipulated as part of the principles of the “BonaRes Repository Data Publication Strategy”. The author expects a high visibility (reputation) of the data and a low effort in data curation prior to publication and metadata provision and credits to his/her scientific findings. Data reusers require clear usage rules and user friendly citation (for example in data collections) to avoid an inflated reference list. In this document we provide clear and simple rules how a DOI is provided for various data and how updates and versions are handled.

Keywords Data citation, BonaRes Repository, data provision, manual, DOI, publication strategy, author, versioning, data collection, monitoring of research data

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Citing soil and agricultural research data

Publication, DOI provision, citation and versioning of data published via the BonaRes Repository

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Document version 1.0 see <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-fm2j-c233>

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Lineage of this document in the order of their relevance for citing data: Major adaptations in the way single tables of a data collection are cited; some possibilities for providing data to a closed community; amendments in glossary; some editorial changes

Content

Glossary / definitions

Author: Person or institution with authorship rights to data and metadata. The author is not necessarily the data provider but can select the data provider as his/her deputy. The author in the sense of this policy is, in case of several authors, the respective main author with the accordant rights. The author is responsible for the quality of the data as well as for the metadata. The author/main author is listed first in the metadata and is the contact person for the data publisher as well as for potential reusers. With respect to the provision of data, we often speak of the creator, data creator or creator of data. We will use the traditional term “author” in this document, as this implies the intellectual effort that forms the basis of the dataset to be published. The author may be supported by the **data steward** in the publishing process.

BonaRes Repository: Facility within ZALF that provides the necessary data infrastructure and maintains it. Deputy of ZALF as publisher in terms of decisions regarding to data. Geographical data from the field of soil and agricultural research and its metadata are permanently stored and published (made available to the public for free reuse) via the BonaRes Repository. All data are stored on ZALF servers and are processed according to the rules of the German Data Protection Act.

Data steward: Contact person for data management issues who provides advice. Tasks include advising during the data publication process on topics such as reformatting data, grouping datasets, describing and adding additional material to the data. The data steward is also the first point of contact for reusers if there are problems with data that has already been published.

Dataset: A digital object that is to be published in the BonaRes Repository, e.g., table, shape file, feature class, image, text, etc., consisting of values that are meaningfully compiled and as highly aggregated as possible. It is at the discretion of the author how to compile records. The author is advised by the data steward. Several interconnected datasets can form a data collection. A dataset consists of at least the combination of data and the associated metadata.

Data collection: Combination of several datasets that are linked to one another by relations. A data collection usually consists of a mother table and one or more child tables.

Date available: Metadata element in the BonaRes Metadata Schema, which marks the date from which on data is available for reuse; typically the date of publishing or end of a possible embargo period.

Date updated: Metadata element in the BonaRes Metadata Schema, which marks the date of the last update of the dataset.

Embargo: Blocking period for the publication of data by the BonaRes Repository on request by the author. Datasets can be published with a planned delay before being publicly available - usually 24 months. The possibility of an embargo is generally regulated via a data policy, which is negotiated individually for large projects or external partners.

Granularity: Number of subdivisions of research data. High granularity is achieved when, for example, related tables are broken up and published individually. Low granularity is achieved when data are meaningfully aggregated (to be aimed for). It is possible to republish part of the data set while observing the associated license. It is possible to combine already existing datasets into new data and to publish them again, taking into account the associated licenses and a necessary level of creativity. In this way, the granularity required for the respective reuse can be achieved.

Landing page: Detailed presentation of the dataset and its metadata within the BonaRes Repository. The landing page is reached when a DOI is entered in a browser (resolving). It enables permanent access to the metadata and thus to data or data collection.

License: A license describes the rules in which form a dataset can be reused. All data are published under a Creative Commons CC-BY license. Metadata are not subject to any restrictions and are openly available (CC-0) and reusable at any time (see: [Creative Commons](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/)¹).

Lineage: History of data generation and storage. The lineage gives data reusers the opportunity to understand important changes/adjustments to the dataset during the data life cycle.

Metadata: Metadata are 'data about data' and contain information on who created the data and how, necessary background information to the data, where it is located, characteristics of the file structure, intellectual property right (IPR) information etc. This descriptive information enables users to judge the usability of the data for their own purposes. BonaRes Metadata consists of elements making data become FAIR. The [BonaRes Metadata Schema](#)² is published.

Publisher: The data-holding facility. For datasets published in the BonaRes Repository, ZALF (Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research) is the publisher. ZALF as the publisher is responsible for the release and distribution of the data.

Record: A single value within data. The smallest unit that can be addressed via citation. Example: A cell in a data table.

Related Identifier: Depiction of the relation of data sets to each other or to other sources such as scientific publications.

Retraction: The aim of the repository is to ensure the reproducibility of research and to improve it overall. Therefore, the hurdles to withdraw a data set are high. However, if serious errors become apparent, it is possible to exclude data from further distribution. This is only available on request.

¹Creative Commons Licenses: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>

² Gärtner, P., Svoboda, N., Kühnert, T., Zoarder, M. A., Heinrich, U. (2017). *The BonaRes Metadata Schema*. BonaRes Series. <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-5pgg-8yvp>

Schöpfungshöhe: The **level of creation**, is a criterion that in copyright law distinguishes copyrighted works from such achievements that are not subject to copyright protection, especially those that are thereby in the public domain.

Threshold of originality: Degree of individual creativity or originality in an intellectual work, which decides whether the work is subject to copyright protection.

Update: Minor changes in the data require an updated version: Version 1.0 updates to version 1.1

Version: Major changes or corrected faults in the data make a new version necessary: Version 1.0 versions to version 2.0

ZALF: Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research

Abstract

The intellectual property right of authors to their data and thus their right to be mentioned by name when data is reused are valuable assets and are therefore stipulated as part of the principles of the “BonaRes Repository Data Publication Strategy”. The author expects a high visibility (reputation) of the data and a low effort in data curation prior to publication and metadata provision and credits to his/her scientific findings. Data reusers require clear usage rules and user friendly citation (for example in data collections) to avoid an inflated reference list. In this document we provide clear and simple rules how a DOI is provided for various data and how updates and versions are handled.

Preamble

The rights of authors to their data and thus their right to be mentioned by name when data is reused are valuable assets and are therefore incorporated in our principles.

The purpose of a persistent digital identifier such as digital object identifier ([DOI](#)³) is to permanently refer to digital objects, facilitating access and credit attribution. ZALF in its role as data publisher adopts and uses DOIs as a worldwide unified standard accepted by the scientific community. Digital objects in the context of this document are research data published in the BonaRes Repository. As a prerequisite for the assignment of a DOI, detailed metadata information must be provided. We implement all metadata elements of [DataCite](#)⁴ and [INSPIRE](#)⁵ within the [BonaRes Metadata Schema](#)⁶ to describe research data with rich metadata including geo-information. With regard to the reproducibility of research results, data should not be changed after the assignment of a DOI. In contrast, the corresponding metadata can be adapted if necessary. ZALF as the publisher hosts and runs the BonaRes Repository and registers DOIs with DataCite according to the [Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles](#)⁷. These following principles foster human understandable and machine-actionable citation:

³ DOI: <http://www.doi.org/>

⁴ DataCite: www.datacite.org

⁵ INSPIRE: <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu>

⁶ Gärtner, P., Svoboda, N., Kühnert, T., Zoader, M. A., Heinrich, U. (2017). *The BonaRes Metadata Schema*. BonaRes Series. <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-5pgg-8yvp>

⁷ Data Citation Synthesis Group: Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles. Martone M. (ed.) San Diego CA: FORCE11; 2014 <https://doi.org/10.25490/a97f-egykh>

- Importance
- Credit and Attribution
- Evidence
- Unique Identification
- Access
- Persistence
- Specificity and Verifiability
- Interoperability and Flexibility

Data publishing principles

1. Research results must be reproducible.
2. The rights of authors must be respected/accepted.
3. Data, especially those generated with the support of public funds, should be made available for free reuse ([Berlin Declaration, 2020⁸](#)).
4. Data can be reused in a user-friendly way.

Strategy and workflow of data publication

ZALF as the data publisher and operator of the BonaRes Repository takes the interests of both data author and reusers into account. The author expects a) high visibility (reputation) of the data and b) low effort in data publication and metadata provision, and credits for his/her scientific findings. Data reusers require clear usage rules and user friendly citation possibilities (for example by using data collections) to avoid an inflated reference list.

In preparation for publication, data should be meaningfully aggregated by the author (granularity). Here, the level of creation (dt. „Schöpfungshöhe“) must also be taken into account in order to justify publication and licensing. The data stewards support this process. It is recommended that scientists publish their data in as few individual data sets as possible (low granularity, high aggregation). For example, individual time slices should not be extracted from a data set (e.g., annual data sets from a series running since 1950) and published individually for the single purpose of generating a large number of DOIs.

The author should already consider possible requirements for reuse during the creation of the data set:

- Can attributes (values) be meaningfully combined in a table?
- Can a dataset be reused meaningfully at the intended level of aggregation?
- Are all attributes necessary for reuse included or can they be accessed via relations to other published tables?
- Do relations (spatial, content) to other datasets exist or are such planned?
- Are additional information available in scientific publications that help to understand this data set?

⁸ Berliner Erklärung zur Digitalen Gesellschaft und wertebasierten digitalen Verwaltung, <https://www.bmi.bund.de/SharedDocs/pressemitteilungen/EN/2020/12/berlin-declaration-digitalization.html>

The author submits the data for publication in the [BonaRes Repository](#)⁹. The data are described with metadata according to the [BonaRes Metadata Schema](#). From this metadata, elements for the DOI are extracted and registered with DataCite. The DOI links to a data object specific landing page in the BonaRes Repository and thus ensures access to the data.

Citation of data from the BonaRes Repository - default case

The citation with all relevant information is part of the metadata access section and can easily be copied.

Authors

This includes the name of all persons whose intellectual work, such as a certain field experiment or laboratory measurements, led to the creation of the data set or collection to be published. The author has accomplished considerable intellectual work (threshold of originality) to create the dataset to be published, deserves recognition (authorship) and takes responsibility for the dataset and the respective metadata. According to good scientific practice (see: [DFG Code of Conduct of Conduct](#)¹⁰), only those authors (co-authors) who have made their own scientific contribution to the creation of the dataset may be listed in the metadata. The responsibility is indivisible, so the main author bears overall responsibility for the respective dataset to the best of his knowledge and conscience („to the best of our knowledge and belief“). Data can also be submitted by a deputy of the author who acts on behalf of the author. The author is supported by the data stewards. In addition to the author, other roles (editor, contributor, etc.) can be included in the metadata. Institutions can also be named as authors. In the case of multiple authors, the order is determined by the first author. All co-authors should have made a substantial contribution.

Example: **Beule, L., Lehrsaar, E., D. Corre, M., Schmidt, M., & Veldkamp, E. (2019).** *Agroforestry promotes soil microbial groups* (Version 1.0). Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF). <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-9nty-5gfa>

Date of publication

This is the point in time (date stamp) at which a data record was released for reuse and citation by others. The "date of publication" results in the year of publication, which is included in the citation.

Example: Grosse, M., & Hierold, W. (2019). *Long-term Field Experiments in Germany* (Version 1.0). Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF). <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-3tr6-mg8r>

If desired, a more precise date can be used to indicate on which day the data became available and citable or when a dataset was updated.

In the case of a dataset that is updated periodically, regularly or continuously, the year of first publication is followed by an increasing version number and the last update (the "Updated" date) to indicate how current it is. Updates can be carried out at different frequencies (see below: Changes / additions to a dataset). Ongoing expansions of a time series change the content of the dataset, but usually do not justify a new version or output of a dataset (see version).

⁹ The BonaRes Repository Upload Tool: <https://upload.bonares.de>

¹⁰ DFG 2019, Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice Code of Conduct, revised version 1.1 (November 2021) ; https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/foerderung/rechtliche_rahmenbedingungen/gute_wissenschaftliche_praxis/kodex_gw_p_en.pdf

Example: Grosse, M. & Hierold, W. (2019). *Long-term Field Experiments in Germany (Version 1.1, Updated 23.1.2020)*. Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF). <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-3tr6-mg8r>

Title

This is the formal title of the dataset. It should contain the object of investigation and the spatial allocation. At the same time, it is to be short and understandable. Further elements such as time period, persons, facilities or project are documented in the metadata.

Example: Steinfurth, K. & Buczko, U. (2019). ***Overview phosphorus fertilization experiments in Germany and Austria*** (Version 1.0). Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF). <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-tndg-696q>

Publisher

The Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF) is the publisher and is mentioned in the citation. DataCite describes the publisher as follows: “The entity that holds, archives, publishes, prints, distributes, releases, issues, or produces the resource. This property will be used to formulate the citation, [...]”

Example: Morshedizad, M. (2018). *Raw data P-XANES measurements* (Version 1.0). **Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF)**. <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-pdy6-hhgs>

Digital object identifier (DOI)

The BonaRes Repository follows the recommendations of [Starr et al. 2015](#)¹¹ and uses the DOI as a persistent identifier to guarantee access to data. The DOI is an identification scheme that can be tracked by machine, offers unambiguous assignment worldwide and is widespread in the scientific community. In addition, the DOI obliges the data to be persistent in the long term. Beyond the reference to ZALF or BonaRes, the DOI suffix does not contain any semantic information. To make the DOI more user-friendly, it is given as a link in the citation ([https://doi.org/\[...\]](https://doi.org/[...])).

Example: Paul, C. & Dönmez, C. (2021). *Dataset of indicators for the assessment of soil-management related ecosystem services*. Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF). <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-mpzr-ja21>

¹¹ Starr J, Castro E, Crosas M, Dumontier M, Downs RR, Duerr R, Haak LL, Haendel M, Herman I, Hodson S, Hourclé J, Kratz JE, Lin J, Nielsen LH, Nurnberger A, Proell S, Rauber A, Sacchi S, Smith A, Taylor M, Clark T. 2015. Achieving human and machine accessibility of cited data in scholarly publications. *Peer J Computer Science* <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.1>

Citation of data from the BonaRes Repository - special cases

The BonaRes Repository offers the possibility of "pre-publication" so that protected access to the data can be granted during the review process of a publication in a scientific journal. The author has the possibility to create a time-limited, password-protected access to the data via DOI resolver (registered, not findable). Contact with the author is established via the landing page. Once the review process is complete, these restrictions are lifted and the DOI is marked as findable in DataCite.

Dataset as part of a data collection

A dataset can be part of a data collection. Such a dataset is cited analogously to a chapter in an anthology/book chapter. If a data collection (consisting of at least two associated datasets) is published, the author defines a parent dataset (for instance geodata). The parent dataset receives a DOI, which directs to the corresponding landing page. All other dependent data are clearly cited via the parent dataset. In this way, either the entire collection or individual or several datasets in the collection can be cited.

Example for citation of a data collection as a whole: Barkusky, D. (2018). *Long-term field experiment V140 Muencheberg from 1963 to 2009 - Plots* (Version 1.0). Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF). <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-bsvy-r418>

Example for citation of one dataset within a data collection: Barkusky, D. (2018). **Table: Irrigation**. In *Long-term field experiment V140 Muencheberg from 1963 to 2009 - Plots* (Version 1.0), Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF). <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-bsvy-r418>

If there are different authors within a data collection, the authors of the main data / parent table are determined in mutual agreement between the authors. Individual, dependent data (child tables) can be cited individually; the respective author or the co-authors and the name of the child table are in front of the citation, followed by referring to the entire collection with the respective authors.

Example for citation of a data collection as a whole with multiple authors: **Barkusky, D., Mustermann, M., Musterfrau, M. & Schrecklicher, H.** (2018). *Long-term field experiment V140 Muencheberg from 1963 to 2009 - Plots* (Version 1.0). Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF). <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-1234-5678> (exemplary DOI)

Example for citation of one data within a data collection with multiple authors: **Schrecklicher, H.** (2018). **Table: Irrigation**. In Barkusky, D., Mustermann, M., Musterfrau, M. & Schrecklicher, H. (2018) *Long-term field experiment V140 Muencheberg from 1963 to 2009 - Plots* (Version 1.0), Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF). <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-1234-5678> (exemplary DOI)

Authors of dependent data (child tables) do not necessarily have to be part of the data collection authors.

Example for citation of data within a data collection; author is not part of the co-authors of the data collection: **Glückspilz, S.** (2018). **Table: plants**. In Barkusky, D., Mustermann, M., Musterfrau, M. & Schrecklicher, H. (2018) *Long-term field experiment V140 Muencheberg from 1963 to 2009 - Plots* (Version 1.0), Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF). <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-1234-5678> (exemplary DOI)

A selection from a published dataset (subset)

A reuser of a published dataset can use a suitable citation method to indicate if only part of the dataset was used. This enables the reader to specifically filter for the addressed data. This is done in the same way as the classic citation method of specifying a page number. The data published via the BonaRes Repository has a consistent structure that is used for this purpose. The data steward can help, for example, to make a selection based on spatial or temporal selection.

Example: Techen, A.-K. (2018). *BonaRes foresight interviews 2017 - qualitative answers* (Version 1.0), **row 10-15**. Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF). <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-3wwy-evt4>

Example: Schmidt, M., Bischel, X., Langhof, M., Seserman, D.M., Swieter, A. & Rudolf, C. (2020). BonaRes-SIGNAL biomass production starting 2016, **Year 2017**. Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF). <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-qp1a-wdcc>

Update of a dataset: small, traceable changes/additions

We differentiate between updates (small changes/additions) and new versions (major changes) of a dataset.

Soil and agricultural data that is published can be supplemented with additional values. Typical examples are weather data or yield data from ongoing trials, which are supplemented by additional years. The addition can be made once or regularly. No major changes are made to the data structure and the new values can be compared to the old ones (units, methods, quality). Original values can be extracted from the latest data set by the reuser with reasonable effort and used “as before” (reproducibility). Any additions made are logged in the BonaRes metadata (documentation and time stamp): Date updated, Lineage and Description.

Example: Grosse, M., & Hierold, W. (2019). *Long-term Field Experiments in Germany* (**Version 1.1, Updated 23.1.2020**). Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF). <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-1234-5678> (exemplary DOI)

Update of a dataset: large, complex changes requiring a new version

New versions typically reflect major changes in the structure of the dataset, sample logs, algorithms, quality control processes, etc. A new version of the dataset usually results in the publication of a new dataset. A change in authorship, for example due to retirement, can also justify a new version. In this case, the previous authors who are no longer part of the author list are added to the metadata as "Contributors".

If incorrect values of a dataset have to be exchanged, values deleted or the structure has been changed, a new version of a dataset must be published. In the case of a new version, a new dataset is published and a new DOI is assigned ([Ball & Duke, 2015¹²](#)). The author decides whether an old dataset should still be accessible via DOI; the person is advised by the data steward. If the data should no longer be accessible, a retraction is necessary (see next chapter).

¹² Ball, A., & Duke, M. (2015). 'How to Track the Impact of Research Data with Metrics'. DCC How-to Guides. Edinburgh: Digital Curation Centre. Available online: <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/how-guides>

The old version of the data set and its metadata remain published and can be accessed via DOI. However, this data will no longer be displayed in the search results in the BonaRes Repository. A reference to the newer version and the reason for the change is entered in the metadata of the older dataset version (metadata elements: Description, related identifier, Lineage). A reference to the old version is given in the metadata of the new dataset version (metadata element: related identifier). It can only be reached via metadata of the new version or via the original DOI link (reproducibility of further research results based on the outdated data). If the publisher becomes aware or is informed that a dataset is incorrect and the author cannot be reached, or if there is no response within a reasonable period, the data in question will be classified as faulty and withdrawn (see retraction).

Example: Barkusky, D. (2021). *Long-term field experiment V140 Muencheberg from (launched in 1963) - Fertilization (Version 2.0)*. Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF).

<https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-8fhj-r52g>

Retraction of an incorrect data set

If a data record contains serious errors that justify severely restricting access, it is retracted (withdrawn). The author/data provider makes the decision on this step with the advice of the data stewards. If a data record is revoked, downloading and further distribution is excluded and is only available on request (for reproducibility purposes). The landing page remains, but an explanatory note is added (“tombstone” landing page).

Previous publications

- 2023/1 Donmez et al. Long-Term Field Experiments: Lift the Agricultural Data Treasure
DOI: [10.20387/BonaRes-7SS0-ZM41](https://doi.org/10.20387/BonaRes-7SS0-ZM41)
- 2022/2 Ittner et al. The impact of subsoil management on the delivery of ecosystem services: An economic valuation for Germany
DOI: [10.20387/BonaRes-WVC6-YJ14](https://doi.org/10.20387/BonaRes-WVC6-YJ14)
- 2022/1 Svoboda et al. Citing soil and agricultural research data - Publication, DOI provision, citation and versioning of data published via the BonaRes Repository
DOI: [10.20387/BonaRes-FM2J-C233](https://doi.org/10.20387/BonaRes-FM2J-C233)
- 2021/2 Stumpf et al. Long-Term-Experiments - methods, standardization and modelling.
DOI: [10.20387/BonaRes-FZK2-TF22](https://doi.org/10.20387/BonaRes-FZK2-TF22)
- 2021/1 Svoboda, N. The BonaRes Data Policy.
DOI: [10.20387/BonaRes-RYCV-30RK](https://doi.org/10.20387/BonaRes-RYCV-30RK)
- 2020/6 Fritsche, J., Svoboda, N. Practical handbook for publishing research data in the BonaRes Repository - Tips & Tricks.
DOI: [10.20387/BonaRes-MVKN-A4MB](https://doi.org/10.20387/BonaRes-MVKN-A4MB)
- 2020/5 Ittner et al. The impact of subsoil management on the delivery of ecosystem services.
DOI: [10.20387/BonaRes-BSZH-QBKN](https://doi.org/10.20387/BonaRes-BSZH-QBKN)
- 2020/4 Wiesmeier et al. CO₂ certificates for carbon sequestration in soils: methods, management practices and limitations.
DOI: [10.20387/BonaRes-NE0G-CE98](https://doi.org/10.20387/BonaRes-NE0G-CE98)
- 2020/3 Ledermüller et al. Arbeitsbericht: Verbesserung des physikalischen Bodenschutzes bei der Wirtschaftsdüngerausbringung im Frühjahr - Herausforderungen und Lösungsansätze.
DOI: [10.20387/BonaRes-ESZ2-NRV9](https://doi.org/10.20387/BonaRes-ESZ2-NRV9)
- 2020/2 Siebert. Energy Crops and Erosion Control in Germany in the Context of the Bioeconomy Strategy.
DOI: [10.20387/BonaRes-TZKG-FNRC](https://doi.org/10.20387/BonaRes-TZKG-FNRC)
- 2020/1 Wiesmeier et al. CO₂-Zertifikate für die Festlegung atmosphärischen Kohlenstoffs in Böden: Methoden, Maßnahmen und Grenzen.
DOI: [10.20387/BonaRes-F8T8-XZ4H](https://doi.org/10.20387/BonaRes-F8T8-XZ4H)
- 2019/6 Hoffmann et al. Data Standards for Soil - and Agricultural Research
DOI: [10.20387/BonaRes-ARM4-66M2](https://doi.org/10.20387/BonaRes-ARM4-66M2)
- 2019/5 Techen & Helming. Policy goals as reference points for interdisciplinary soil research
DOI: [10.20387/BonaRes-52TA-02M9](https://doi.org/10.20387/BonaRes-52TA-02M9)
- 2019/4 Paul & Helming. Handbook of Soil-Related Impact Assessment.
DOI: [10.20387/BonaRes-6DJM-E22M](https://doi.org/10.20387/BonaRes-6DJM-E22M)

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BonaRes is short for “Soil as a Sustainable Resource for the Bioeconomy”. The focus lies on the sustainable use of soils as a limited resource. BonaRes extends the evidence base for scientists and decision-makers regarding the soil systems to improve the productivity of soils and other soil functions while developing new strategies for a sustainable management of soils.

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